

HYDROCHAR-BASED FLAME RETARDANTS FROM BREWERS' SPENT GRAIN FOR HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Biocomposites, Hydrochar, Flame resistance, Mechanical properties, Phytic acid

ABSTRACT

In this study, a sustainable flame-retardant biocomposite was developed by incorporating hydrochar (HC) derived from Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG) into a polylactic acid (PLA) matrix. HC was produced via hydrothermal carbonization (HTC), yielding a porous, carbon-rich material characterized by a high content of oxygen-containing functional groups. The filler was further functionalized with phytic acid (PA) to introduce phosphorus-based flame-retardant functionalities (HC-P). The effectiveness of the modification was confirmed through FT-IR, while SEM-EDS, BET and elemental analysis were used to assess the structural and surface properties of HC. PLA composites containing 20 wt.% of HC and HC-P were prepared via melt blending and compression molding, and characterized by TGA, DSC, DMA, and flexural testing. HC incorporation led to earlier thermal degradation and reduced mechanical performance, attributed to poor interfacial adhesion and filler aggregation. However, PA functionalization improved thermal stability and partially restored mechanical properties by enhancing filler-matrix compatibility and dispersion. Cone calorimeter tests revealed that the HC-P composite exhibited improved flame-retardant performance, with reductions of 15% in peak heat release rate (pHRR), 13% in total smoke release (TSR), 12.5% in specific extinction area (SEA), and 12.9% in MARHE compared to the unmodified composite. These results highlight the dual role of phytic acid in promoting char formation and limiting flammable volatile release, demonstrating the potential of functionalized hydrochar as an effective bio-based flame retardant for PLA composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of manufacturing industries has increased the demand for materials with improved strength, lower density, reduced cost, and enhanced sustainability. Composite materials have

emerged as one of the materials that can meet this growing demand. Growing environmental awareness has highlighted the impact of plastic pollution and fossil fuel use, driving industries to adopt renewable raw materials and develop biobased polymers to reduce environmental impact [1]. Among biopolymers, polylactic acid (PLA) stands out as a promising material produced from renewable sources like corn starch and sugarcane [2]. Its biodegradability, biocompatibility, and suitable mechanical performance have made it a widely used alternative to traditional petroleum-based plastics in various fields, including packaging, textiles, biomedical applications, and composite materials. However, biopolymers like PLA are generally more expensive than petroleum-based plastics, limiting their broader adoption [3]. A common strategy to reduce costs while preserving environmental benefits involves creating biocomposites by partially replacing the polymer with low-cost, natural waste-derived fillers [4]. Moreover, PLA exhibits certain drawbacks that limit its use in more demanding applications, as low thermal stability, brittleness, and high flammability [5]. To address these limitations, recent research has focused on incorporating functional reinforcement to enhance performance and lower production costs.

Various additives and fillers—such as antioxidants, plasticizers, stiffeners, and flame retardants—are widely used to enhance specific polymer properties. However, some stiffening fillers fail to balance stiffness and toughness, and many conventional fillers raise environmental and health concerns due to their toxicity (e.g., phthalates, PBDEs [6]). As a result, there is increasing interest in greener alternatives that combine performance with safety. Carbon-based materials like carbon nanotubes, carbon black, biochar, and graphene [7,8] are particularly promising due to their high surface area, carbon content, and hydrophobicity. However, materials such as graphene and nanotubes remain costly and complex to produce. Biochar (BC) is a sustainable carbon-based filler with high thermal stability, hardness, surface area, chemical stability, and electrical conductivity [9]. These properties make it a promising alternative to conventional fillers for improving the mechanical, electrical, and flame-resistant performance of PLA-, HDPE-, and PP-based composites. Among carbon-based materials, hydrochar (HC) is emerging as a sustainable and promising filler for polymer composites, although it remains less studied than biochar, carbon black, or carbon nanotubes. HC is produced via hydrothermal carbonization (HTC), a low-temperature (180–300 °C), water-based thermochemical process that converts wet biomass under autogenous pressure [10]. Unlike pyrolysis, HTC allows direct processing of high-moisture feedstocks, such as agricultural residues or food waste, eliminating energy-intensive drying and offering higher solid yields. These features support its economic viability and align with circular economy principles by converting organic waste into valuable carbon-based materials. When combined with biodegradable polymers like PLA, HC contributes to the development of sustainable, carbon-neutral or even carbon-negative composites. In this work, we propose hydrochar (HC) derived from Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG) via hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) as a sustainable carbon-based filler for PLA composites. BSG is the primary by-product of the brewing industry, accounting for around 85% of its total waste, with an estimated annual output of 25–40 million tonnes globally and 3.4 million tonnes within the EU [11]. This lignocellulosic residue is rich in organic matter but contains a high moisture content (70–90 wt.%), making it prone to microbial decomposition and the development of unpleasant odors. In warm climates, its shelf life may be limited to 7–10 days, posing challenges for storage and transportation [12]. As a result, BSG is often disposed of through unsustainable practices such as landfilling. HTC offers an effective valorization route by processing wet biomass without prior drying, making it particularly suitable for BSG and contributing to circular waste management strategies. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no study has investigated the use of hydrochar (HC) derived from Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG) as a filler in polymer composite materials. Only a few studies have explored HC obtained from other biomass sources for composite applications. Ye et al. conducted a comparative study on HC and biochar from wood chips as fillers in PBAT-based biodegradable composites. HC acted as a nucleating agent and influenced the hydrophobicity of the composites. Unlike biochar, which increased stiffness at the expense of toughness, HC provided an improved balance between stiffness and toughness, with optimal performance achieved at 10 wt.% HC treated at 300 °C [13]. Nizamuddin et al. developed PLA-based composites incorporating 5–20 wt.% HC from rice husk via melt processing. The addition of HC significantly increased the tensile modulus (from 2.63 to 4.24 GPa at 20 wt.%) due to mechanical interlocking and polymer infiltration into HC pores. However, tensile strength and elongation at break decreased, attributed to weak interfacial adhesion and particle agglomeration. HC also acted as a nucleating agent and enhanced the thermal stability of the composites [14]. Bejenari et al. investigated

HC from spruce bark waste in an aromatic bio-epoxy resin system, where HC acted as both a filler and a co-reactant in the crosslinking process. This dual role led to increased reaction enthalpy, a reduced curing temperature range, and significantly improved thermal stability and hardness, demonstrating HC's potential to produce stiffer and more sustainable materials [15]. Therefore, using HC as a filler in biopolymers offers a promising strategy for developing biocomposite materials by lowering costs, potentially enhancing the polymer's mechanical properties, and adding value to waste in accordance with circular economy principles. However, one of the main problems with biocomposite materials persists: their poor fire resistance. Biopolymers like PLA are inherently highly flammable [16]. Flame retardants (FRs) are essential for improving the fire safety of composite materials by preventing ignition and slowing combustion. While halogen-based FRs were widely adopted in the 1970s for their high efficiency at low loadings, their use has raised serious environmental and health concerns due to the release of toxic gases and persistent pollutants. As a result, increasing regulations and environmental awareness have driven the development of halogen-free, bio-based flame retardants as safer and more sustainable alternatives [17]. Among halogen-free alternatives, phosphorus-based flame retardants are gaining significant interest due to their structural versatility, variable phosphorus content, and oxidation states (0 to +5), which enable tailored flame-retardant mechanisms suited to different polymer matrices [18,19]. Incorporating flame retardants (FRs) directly into the polymer matrix is the most common method to enhance fire resistance of bio-based composites. However, this approach often results in compatibility issues between the FRs and PLA, negatively impacting the mechanical properties of the composites due to increased melt viscosity and potential phase separation [20,21]. An alternative strategy involves grafting or adsorbing the FR onto the filler, thus improving fire resistance without compromising composite integrity, especially in systems using hydrophilic FRs and hydrophobic polymer matrices, such as PLA [22]. In this paper, we aim to address key challenges associated with polymeric biocomposites, such as high cost and poor fire resistance, by developing a PLA-based biocomposite reinforced with hydrochar (HC) derived from beer production waste. To enhance fire resistance, we also propose the surface modification of the filler using phytic acid. Phytic acid (PA), with its high phosphorus content (~28%) and non-toxic, eco-friendly profile, is gaining attention as a sustainable flame retardant and alternative to halogenated compounds [23]. It acts in both the condensed and gas phases, promoting char formation and releasing phosphorus radicals that quench flame-propagating species, while generating inert gases that dilute combustible elements [24]. In composite materials, PA has been used to modify reinforcing phases to enhance flame resistance. Liu et al. treated ramie fibers with PA, increasing LOI and char yield but reducing mechanical strength, which was mitigated through hybridization with glass fibers [25]. Costes et al. improved PLA flame retardancy by melt blending lignin with PA, achieving a 44% reduction in peak heat release rate, UL-94 V-2 classification, improved thermal stability, and enhanced elongation at break [26]. In the literature, one study reports the use of carbon-based materials as fillers in combination with phytic acid: Zhong et al. prepared flame-retardant bamboo biochar (mBC) via hydrogen peroxide oxidation followed by modification with phytic acid and urea to add phosphorus and nitrogen groups. Incorporating 10 wt.% mBC into PLA improved flame retardancy, achieving UL-94 V-0 and raising the LOI from 20.7% to 28.3%. Cone calorimeter tests showed a decrease in ignition time (63 to 38 s at 20 wt.% mBC) and reduced heat release due to stable char formation. Despite some loss in mechanical strength from filler-matrix incompatibility, performance remained acceptable [27]. In this study, hydrochar was produced from Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG). Compared to biochar, hydrochar naturally possesses a surface rich in oxygen-containing functional groups and exhibits a highly porous structure. These features eliminate the need for oxidative pretreatment, thereby avoiding the associated safety risks. The use of hydrochar not only reduces energy consumption during filler production but also makes the modification process more sustainable. The produced hydrochar was characterized for its structure by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) coupled with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), its chemical composition through elemental analysis, and its porosity by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) measurements. Following characterization, the hydrochar was modified by reaction with phytic acid. This modification was carried out in aqueous solution at room temperature, with pH adjustment facilitating the formation of ionic and hydrogen bonds. The modified filler (HC-P) was analyzed by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) to confirm the effectiveness of the surface modification and subsequently

incorporated into polylactic acid (PLA) matrices at a loading of 20 wt.%. The resulting composites were evaluated for their mechanical, thermal, and flame retardant properties using cone calorimetry.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIALS

A PLA Luminy® LX175 (96% L-isomer), provided by TotalEnergies Corbion, was utilized as the polymer matrix. Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG) was provided by research center CERB (Italian Brewing Research Centre, Perugia, Italy). Phytic acid solution 50 % (w/w) in H₂O and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were obtained from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2 HYDROCHAR SYNTHESIS AND COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING

Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG), with a moisture content of 83.5%, was first homogenized by grinding and then mixed with distilled water to obtain a dry-to-water ratio of 1:2. The resulting mixture was placed in an autoclave hydrothermal reactor, where hydrochar (HC) was produced through hydrothermal carbonization (HTC). The reaction was conducted at 230 °C for 4 hours.

5g of hydrochar were reacted with 13.1 mL (14.4 mmol) of phytic acid. The pH was adjusted to 4.5 using sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 hours. The modified hydrochar (HC-P) was then collected by filtration.

Fabrication of the PLA reinforced with untreated hydrochar (PLA-HC) and PLA reinforced with modified hydrochar (PLA_{HC}-P) composites was performed using Brabender-like equipment (Rheocord EC, Haake Inc.) and a lab hydraulic press (Collin model P400E) to process them into plates (100mm × 100mm × 4mm). Before compounding, the HC and HC-P as well as the PLA pellets were dried in a vacuum oven at 70 °C for 4 h. The micro compounder was used to mix HC and HC-P with PLA setting the rotation speed of 60 rpm at 180 °C for 5 min. The PLA composites were then compression molded at 180 °C using a pressure profile as follows: 2 min at 0 bar – 1 min at 5 bar – 1 min at 10 bar and 1 min at 20 bar. Finally, the cooling step down to room temperature was carried out while maintaining the material at the maximum pressure set (20 bar). The reinforcement content was kept at 20 wt.%.

2.3 CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES

The effectiveness of hydrochar (HC) modification with phytic acid was evaluated using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR). Spectra were recorded with a Bruker VERTEX 70 spectrometer equipped with a diamond attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory. Measurements were performed in the mid-infrared range (400–4000 cm⁻¹) at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, averaging 128 scans per sample.

The surface morphology of the hydrochar (HC) was examined using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) combined with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS). Imaging was performed on a Tescan Mira3 system at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Prior to analysis, the samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold to enhance conductivity.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed in accordance with ISO 11358, using a TG209 F1 Libra instrument (Netzsch). Samples were heated from room temperature to 800 °C at a constant rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out in accordance with ISO 11357 using a DSC 300 Caliris (Netzsch), under a nitrogen flow of 40 mL/min. The thermal program consisted of a heating–cooling–heating cycle from 25 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. Melting and crystallization temperatures, along with the degree of crystallinity (X_c , see Equation 1), were determined as the average values from three independent measurements:

$$\chi_c = \frac{(\Delta H_m - \Delta H_{cc})}{\Delta H_m^0 \times \phi} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_{cc} and ΔH_m represent the cold crystallization and melting enthalpies of the PLA composites, respectively; ϕ is the weight fraction of PLA in the composite; and ΔH_m^0 (93 J/g) is the enthalpy of fusion for 100% crystalline PLA [28].

Elemental composition was analyzed using a UNICUBE[®] elemental analyzer.

Surface area and porosity were measured by N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms at –196 °C using a Micromeritics Triflex analyzer. Samples were outgassed at 300 °C for 4 hours before analysis. Isotherms ($p/p_0 = 0.01–0.99$) were analyzed with 3Flex software (v4.05), and the BET equation was applied to calculate the specific surface area.

The thermal conductivity of the composites was measured using a TCi C-Therm thermal conductivity analyzer (C-Therm Technologies Ltd., Fredericton, Canada).

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was used to evaluate the thermo-mechanical behavior of the materials in the solid state under oscillatory loading. The storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E''), and damping factor ($\tan \delta = E''/E'$) were recorded as a function of temperature. Tests were performed in three-point bending mode using a DMA 242 E Artemis instrument (Netzsch), in accordance with ISO 6721. Specimens ($60 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$) were heated from 25 °C to 75 °C at a rate of 2 °C/min, with a constant oscillation frequency of 1 Hz.

Flexural tests were performed on $80 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ specimens using a Zwick/Roell Z2.5 machine, following ISO 178 (span-to-thickness ratio 16:1, crosshead speed 5 mm/min).

Fire behavior was evaluated using an oxygen consumption-based cone calorimeter (CCT), specifically the FFT Cone Calorimeter model from Fire Testing Technology Limited. In accordance with ISO 5660 standards, tests were conducted with an incident heat flux of 35 kW/m². The specimens, placed horizontally under a cone-shaped heater, measured $100 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$ with a thickness of 4 mm. Each formulation was tested using three replicate samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The raw material, Brewers' Spent Grains (BSG), and the resulting hydrochar (HC) produced via hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) were morphologically characterized by SEM analysis as shown in Figure 1. The BSG (Figure 1a) exhibits a compact and relatively smooth surface morphology, with aggregated structures and limited visible porosity. After HTC treatment, a substantial morphological transformation is observed (Figure 1b): the HC displays a more fragmented and porous structure, characterized by rougher surfaces and irregular agglomerates. This change is consistent with the partial carbonization and structural reorganization of the lignocellulosic matrix induced by the HTC process.

Figure 1: SEM analysis of (a) as-received Brewers' Spent Grains (BSG) and (b) hydrochar (HC)

Elemental analysis was performed on both dried BSG and the resulting hydrochar. The raw BSG exhibited a composition of 46.3% carbon, 4.71% hydrogen, 3.79% nitrogen, and 0.063% sulfur. After HTC treatment, the hydrochar showed a composition of 60.5% carbon, 6.9% hydrogen, 2.8% nitrogen, and 0.3% sulfur. The observed increase in carbon and hydrogen content, together with the relative decrease in nitrogen, reflects the fundamental chemical transformations induced by the HTC process. Specifically, HTC promotes the removal of nitrogen-containing compounds via volatilization or dissolution in the aqueous phase, resulting in a more carbon-enriched solid. This behavior is consistent with findings reported by Kruse et al., who attributed the decrease in nitrogen content to the degradation

of proteins into amino acids and subsequently into volatile species such as ammonia and amines. The preferential loss of nitrogen and retention of carbon-rich structures leads to a more aromatic and condensed hydrochar, particularly when protein-rich feedstocks like BSG are used [29]. The BET specific surface area of HC was measured at 6.63 m²/g, while the pore volume derived from BJH analysis remains low, suggesting the presence of a predominantly mesoporous to macroporous network. These textural features are consistent with those typically observed in non-activated hydrochars produced under mild hydrothermal conditions [30,31]. The hydrochar was then functionalized with phytic acid units via a reaction carried out at room temperature using water as the solvent. This functionalization aimed to introduce phosphate groups onto the hydrochar surface, potentially enhancing its effectiveness as a flame retardant for biocomposites. The FT-IR spectra of HC show a broad band between 3100 and 3700 cm⁻¹ attributed to O–H stretching vibrations in hydroxyl and carboxyl groups. Peaks at 2921 and 2855 cm⁻¹ correspond to aliphatic C–H stretching and deformation vibrations [32]. The band at around 1060 cm⁻¹ is associated with β -glycosidic bonds in cellulose and hemicellulose [33]. An absorption peak near 1515 cm⁻¹ indicates aromatic ring stretching vibrations, suggesting the presence of aromatic structures [34]. The peak at approximately 1700 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C=O groups, while bands in the range 1030–1160 cm⁻¹ relate to cellulose components [33]. The FT-IR spectrum of HC-P showed new signals at 1059 cm⁻¹ and 921 cm⁻¹. Phytic acid typically exhibits signals associated with the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of P–O–C groups at 1071 cm⁻¹ and 996 cm⁻¹, respectively [35]. The shift in the newly observed signals may suggest interactions between phytic acid and functional groups on the hydrochar surface [36]. PLA-based composites were prepared by incorporating 20 wt.% of either HC or HC-P as reinforcing agents. The thermal degradation behavior of neat PLA and its composites with HC and HC-P was investigated by TGA, as reported in Table 1. The incorporation of HC into the PLA matrix leads to an earlier degradation, as evidenced by the decrease in T_{5%}, T_{10%}, and T_{max} values. This behavior can be attributed to two main mechanisms. The first is related to the presence of HC, a carbonaceous material with a porous structure and high surface area, which facilitates the formation of thermally conductive networks within the PLA matrix. Indeed, the thermal conductivity of PLA reinforced with HC increased by approximately 80% compared to neat PLA, enhancing heat transfer efficiency throughout the material. As a result, the composite heats up more uniformly and rapidly under thermal stress, leading to an earlier onset of thermal degradation [37]. The second possible mechanism involves chemical interactions between the biochar surface and the PLA matrix. Similar observations have been reported for PLA composites containing grapevine-derived biochar (GVC), where the filler was found to catalyze the scission of PLA macromolecular chains. This resulted in a reduced average molecular weight and a narrower molecular weight distribution. Such molecular-level degradation can also contribute to the earlier thermal decomposition observed in PLA/HC composites [38]. Interestingly, the composite containing phytic acid-modified hydrochar (PLA_HC-P) shows slightly delayed degradation compared to PLA_HC, with T_{5%} and T_{10%} values of 301.1 °C and 332.6 °C, respectively. Its T_{max} (368.1 °C) is also close to that of neat PLA (369.6 °C). While thermal conductivity remains similar to PLA_HC, this delayed degradation suggests a stabilizing effect of phytic acid. Such behavior may be attributed to phosphorus-containing groups from phytic acid, which are known to promote char formation and interfere with radical degradation pathways [39]. Moreover, the final residue increases significantly with the addition of HC (8.93%) and even more so in PLA_HC-P (10.3%), compared to neat PLA (1.5%). This trend reflects the presence of the carbon-rich filler and the additional contribution of phytic acid, which is known to promote carbonization reactions and enhance char yield during thermal decomposition [40].

	T _{5%} °C	T _{10%} °C	T _{max} °C	Residue wt. %
PLA	340.2	347.3	369.6	1.5
PLA_HC	297.3	319.2	359.0	8.9
PLA_HC-P	301.1	332.6	368.1	10.3

Table 1: TGA results of PLA, PLA_HC and PLA_HC-P

Composites materials were then characterized by DSC analysis (Table 2). The incorporation of 20 wt.% hydrochar (HC) into PLA resulted in a decrease in the glass transition temperature (T_g). This reduction may be attributed to a combination of factors. On one hand, the presence of polar functional groups on the HC surface can increase the free volume between PLA chains, enhancing chain mobility and thereby lowering T_g [41,42]. On the other hand, the possible presence of residual moisture and hydroxyl groups on HC may have contributed to partial degradation of PLA chains during melt mixing, leading to a lower molecular weight and, consequently, a reduced T_g [43]. However, an increase in the crystallinity was observed. This is likely due to the ability of HC particles to act as nucleating agents, promoting crystal growth and enhancing overall crystallinity [13]. This effect thus seems to coexist with an increase in the amorphous fraction, as indicated by the shift in T_g . This could be the result of heterogeneity in HC dispersion or partial PLA degradation, leading to localized changes in chain mobility and crystal structure. PLA reinforced with phytic acid-functionalized hydrochar (PLA_HC-P) showed a slight increase in T_g compared to PLA_HC. This may be attributed to improved interfacial interactions between HC and the PLA matrix, promoted by phytic acid, which can reduce the interfacial free volume and limit chain mobility [26]. Nonetheless, the T_g remained lower than that of neat PLA, and a reduction in crystallinity was observed in comparison to PLA_HC.

This behavior could be explained by multiple concurrent phenomena, including a potential and mild plasticizing effect of phytic acid on the PLA matrix, which can increase chain flexibility and thus reducing crystallinity [44,45].

Sample	T_g (°C)	T_{cc} (°C)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_{cc} (J g ⁻¹)	ΔH_m (J g ⁻¹)	χ_c (%)
PLA	59.6	117.6	147.9	11.4	15.9	4.9
PLA-HC	53.6	118.9	147.2	19.1	23.8	6.3
PLA_HC_P	54.8	115.9	146.7	22.5	24.8	3.1

Table 2: DSC results of PLA, PLA_HC and PLA_HC-P

Dynamic mechanical analysis (Table 3) provided further insights into the thermomechanical behavior of the composites. The storage modulus (E') of PLA_HC was significantly lower than that of neat PLA, suggesting a plasticizing effect induced by the presence of hydrochar. This reduction in stiffness may be attributed to the limited interfacial adhesion between HC and the PLA matrix, and the tendency of HC particles to form aggregates, which can act as stress concentrators and disrupt efficient load transfer[46]. Consistent with DSC findings, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PLA_HC was shifted to lower values, indicating increased chain mobility likely related to the presence of polar groups on HC and possible partial degradation of PLA during processing. Interestingly, the PLA_HC-P sample exhibited a moderate increase in storage modulus compared to PLA_HC and a less pronounced shift in T_g . This suggests that the phytic acid functionalization may improve compatibility and interfacial interaction between HC and the PLA matrix [26].

Sample	E' (MPa)			T_g (°C)
	at 40 °C	at 50 °C	at 60 °C	
PLA	3229	3130	398	63.8
PLA_HC	2487	527	22	58.2
PLA_HC-P	2687	2023	20	59.5

Table 3: DMA results of PLA, PLA_HC and PLA_HC-P

The flexural tests showed (Table 4) a decrease in flexural strength and elastic modulus for both PLA_HC and PLA_HC-P composites compared to neat PLA, with strain at maximum load remaining relatively unchanged. Although DSC analysis revealed an increase in crystallinity for PLA_HC, the mechanical weakening observed can be attributed to poor interfacial adhesion and the formation of HC aggregates, which act as stress concentrators and impair effective load transfer [13]. Conversely, PLA_HC-P exhibited reduced crystallinity relative to PLA_HC, which might lower stiffness. Nevertheless, interfacial interactions due to phytic acid functionalization help recover mechanical performance by minimizing aggregation and promoting better stress transfer. This balance results in PLA_HC-P having somewhat better flexural properties than PLA_HC, despite the decreased crystallinity.

	Strain %	Flexural Strength MPa	Flexural modulus GPa
PLA	3.9 ± 0.1	98.6 ± 1.7	3.5 ± 0.2
PLA_HC	3.2 ± 0.3	53.5 ± 3.0	2.5 ± 0.2
PAL-HC-P	3.9 ± 0.1	57.0 ± 4.3	2.5 ± 0.7

Table 4: Flexural results of PLA, PLA_HC and PLA_HC-P

The PLA composite reinforced with phytic-acid-modified hydrochar (PLA_HC-P) showed notable improvements in fire behavior compared to the unmodified system (PLA_HC). Specifically, cone calorimetry revealed a 15% reduction in peak heat release rate (pHRR), a 13% decrease in total smoke release (TSR), a 12.5% reduction in specific extinction area (SEA), and a 12.9% decrease in maximum average rate of heat emission (MARHE). These results indicate that the incorporation of phytic acid enhances the flame-retardant performance of the composite. The phosphorus-rich structure of phytic acid likely promotes the formation of a stable and protective char layer during combustion, which limits heat and mass transfer. Moreover, the modification alters the thermal degradation pathway, reducing the release of flammable volatiles and smoke. This suggests a synergistic flame-retardant effect, combining condensed-phase char promotion and gas-phase flame inhibition, resulting in improved fire safety of the PLA-based composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the potential of hydrochar (HC) derived from Brewers' Spent Grain (BSG) as a sustainable filler for PLA-based biocomposites. The hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) process enabled the direct valorization of wet agro-industrial waste into a porous, carbon-rich material without the need for drying or activation. Structural, morphological, and chemical characterization of the HC—through SEM-EDS, FT-IR, BET, elemental analysis, and Boehm titration—confirmed the development of a heterogeneous, oxygen-functionalized surface suitable for further chemical modification. Surface functionalization with phytic acid (PA) introduced phosphorus-containing groups onto the HC, as confirmed by FT-IR analysis, with the aim of enhancing flame retardancy and improving compatibility with the PLA matrix. Thermal analysis indicated that HC alone tended to promote earlier degradation of PLA, while phytic acid modification delayed degradation and enhanced char formation, suggesting increased thermal stability. Calorimetric data showed changes in crystallinity behavior, with HC promoting nucleation and PA-modified HC slightly suppressing it, likely due to altered filler–matrix interactions.

Dynamic mechanical and flexural tests highlighted a reduction in stiffness and strength with HC, partially recovered when the filler was functionalized, confirming the positive effect of PA on dispersion and interfacial adhesion. Cone calorimeter tests showed that the addition of phytic-acid-modified hydrochar (PLA_HC-P) resulted in improvements in fire behavior, with reductions of 15% in pHRR, 13% in TSR, 12.5% in SEA, and 12.9% in MARHE compared to the unmodified composite. Overall, the combined use of hydrochar and phytic acid offers a promising strategy to produce bio-based composites with improved thermal stability, enhanced flame retardancy, and acceptable mechanical properties, while promoting circular economy principles through the upcycling of food industry residues.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financed by the European Union - NextGenerationEU (National Sustainable Mobility Center CN00000023, Italian Ministry of University and Research Decree n. 1033 - 17/06/2022, Spoke 11 - Innovative Materials & Lightweighting). The opinions expressed are those of the authors only and should not be considered as representative of the European Union or the European Commission's official position. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

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